

A Business Intelligence Approach to Investigating the Determinants of Indonesia's Economic Progress

Data Source

In this paper, we conducted research on the six factors influencing economic progress in Indonesia. The values of these factors were obtained from data collected through the Indonesian Central Bureau of Statistics (BPS).

BPS is a Non-Ministerial Government Institution that provides statistical data in Indonesia based on population censuses, inter-census population surveys, the Indonesian contraceptive prevalence survey, the Indonesian demographic and health survey, and from population registration. The following are the data sources we used:

1. Gross Regional Domestic Product per Capita at Current Prices by Province (2022)

<https://www.bps.go.id/id/statistics-table/3/YWtoQIRVZzNiMU5qUIVOSIRFeFZiRT R4VDJOTVVUMDkjMw==/produk-domestik-regional-bruto-per-kapita-atas-dasar-harga-berlaku-menurut-provinsi--ribu-rupiah---2022.html?year=2022>

Notes: This data is used to obtain the average income of the population with the calculation: Total Gross Regional Domestic Product/12.

2. Percentage of Poor Population by Province and Region (2023)

<https://www.bps.go.id/id/statistics-table/2/MTkyIzI=/persentase-penduduk-miskin--p0--menurut-provinsi-dan-daerah--persen-.html>

3. Domestic Investment by Province (2023)

<https://www.bps.go.id/id/statistics-table/2/NzkzIzI=/realisasi-investasi-penanaman-modal-dalam-negeri-menurut-provinsi-investasi-.html>

4. Human Development Index / HDI by Province (2023)

<https://www.bps.go.id/id/statistics-table/2/NDk0IzI=/-metode-baru--indeks-pembangunan-manusia-menurut-provinsi.html>

5. Population Growth Rate by Province (2020-2021)

<https://www.bps.go.id/id/statistics-table/1/MTI2OCMx/rata-rata-laju-pertumbuhan-penduduk-menurut-provinsi--1971---2022.html>

6. Open Unemployment Rate by Province (August 2023)

<https://www.bps.go.id/id/statistics-table/2/NTQzIzI=/tingkat-pengangguran-terbuka-menurut-provinsi--persen-.html>

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